

δ (CCl_4) 1.6 (6H, s, 2CH_3), 1.8–2.0 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2), 2.1 (3H, s, COCH_3), 4.6–5.1 (5H, m, $\text{CH}_2=\text{C}$, $\text{CH}_2=\text{C}$ and $\text{CHO}-$); **1b** (Found: C, 72.4; H, 10.0. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 72.5; H, 9.8%); ν_{max} 2980, 2860, 1750, 1650, 1450, 960 and 800 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.3 (3H, bs, $\sphericalangle\text{CH}_2$), 1.5–1.7 (6H, d, $(\text{H}_2\text{C})_2\text{C}=\text{C}$), 2.0 (3H, s, $\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$), 2.2 (2H, t, $\text{H}-\text{C}-\text{C}-\text{H}$), 4.6–5.2 (4H, m, $\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{H}$ and $\text{H}-\text{C}(\text{OAc})-\text{C}(\text{OH}_2)-\text{H}$).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support.

References

1. T. NEGISHI, M. UCHIDA, T. ISHIWATARI, S. ASANO, K. NAKAGAWA, Y. TAMAKI and K. MORI, *Appl. Entomol. Zool.*, 1980, **15**, 328.
2. M. UCHIDA, K. NAKAGAWA, T. NEGISHI, S. ASANO and K. MORI, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1981, **45**, 869.
3. B. A. BIRRT-LEONHARDT, D. S. MORENO, M. SCHWARZ, H. S. FOSTER, J. R. PLIMMER and E. D. DEVILBISS, *Life Sci.*, 1980, **27**, 399.
4. K. SHANKARAN and A. S. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, **21**, 542.
5. V. N. ODINOKOV, V. R. AKHMETOVA, L. P. BOTSMAN, G. A. TOLSTIKOV and A. M. MOISEENOV, *Khim. Prir. Soedin.*, 1985, 259.
6. V. N. ODINOKOV, V. R. AKHMETOVA, L. P. BOTSMAN, G. A. TOLSTIKOV, B. A. OHEKIS, V. V. VSELOVSKII and A. M. MOISEENOV, *Zh. Org. Khim.*, 1985, **21**, 990.
7. E. S. RAO and J. S. YADAV, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 1174.
8. Y. FALL, VAN BAC N and Y. LONGLOIS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 3611.
9. E. J. COREY and J. W. SUGGS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 2617.

Preparation of some 1-Guanyl/(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-3-phenylamino-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles

RAJEEV JAIN*, PRATIBHA PANDEW and SUSHMA JAIN
School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University,
Gwalior-474 011

Manuscript received 26 October 1988, revised 30 October 1989,
accepted 21 November 1989

PYRAZOLE and isoxazole derivatives have been reported to possess various biological activities¹. The present communication deals with the preparation of some new pyrazole derivatives of type **1b** with an intention to synthesise biologically active products.

Substituted benzene diazonium chloride was condensed with acetoacetanilide to get **1a**. The product was refluxed with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine or aminoguanidine nitrate in acetic acid to get **1b**. The structural assignments of the products were

based on their elemental analysis and uv, ir and pmr spectral data.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a specord Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 instrument using TMS as an internal standard. All the melting points are uncorrected.

2-Arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione^a: Appropriate aniline (0.01 mol) was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 ml) and water (4 ml) and the solution was cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. To it, an ice-cooled aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.7 g) was added in small portions. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered into already cooled mixture of acetoacetanilide (0.01 mol), sodium acetate (8.0 g) and water (25 ml) with stirring. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from water–dimethylformamide mixture, m.p. 110° (Found: N, 14.50. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: N, 14.94%); M^+ at m/e 281.

Nmr spectra of **1a** revealed signals at δ 2.6 ± 0.06 (COCH_3), 12.90–13.50 (broad, $\text{NH}-(-\text{NH}-\text{N}=\text{C})$), and 7.00–8.20 (ArH for two phenyl rings). It appears that the small shift of the CH_3 signal to lower field is due to the hydrogen bonding and therefore the following are the correct structures for these compounds.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE PYRAZOLES*

Sl. no.**	R ₁	Mol. formula	Yield %	M.p. °C
1.	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅	60	82
2.	2-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₅	65	155
3.	4-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₅	62	120
4.	2-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅	62	195
5.	3-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅	60	180
6.	4-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅	55	195
7.	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₅	55	165
8.	4-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	62	140
9.	2-NO ₂ , 4-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅	60	150
10.	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	65	120
11.	2-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	60	150
12.	4-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	60	154
13.	2-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	55	200
14.	3-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	60	201
15.	4-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	58	230
16.	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	60	140
17.	3-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl ₂	65	140
18.	4-Br	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ ClBr	65	180
19.	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₄	55	126
20.	2-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄	50	135
21.	4-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄	50	150
22.	2-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₆	52	160
23.	3-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₆	54	195
24.	4-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₆	50	178
25.	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₆	52	119
26.	3-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	50	112
27.	4-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	50	135
28.	2-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₆	52	136
29.	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	55	108
30.	2-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	50	138
31.	4-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	52	130
32.	2-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₆ Cl	50	188
33.	3-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₆ Cl	50	160
34.	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₆ Cl	55	132
35.	3-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₄ Cl ₂	54	130
36.	4-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₄ Cl ₂	50	160
37.	4-Br	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₄ ClBr	50	170
38.	2-NO ₂ , 4-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₅ Cl ₂	52	200

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

**For compounds sl. nos. 1-9, R₂=H, R₃=-C(=NH).NH₂.HNO₂; for sl. nos. 10-18, R₂=2-Cl, R₃=-C(=NH).NH₂.HNO₂; for sl. nos. 19-28, R₂=H, R₃=2,4-DNP; for sl. nos. 29-38, R₂=2-Cl, R₃=2,4-DNP.

The ir spectra also support the above structures. The presence of the CO stretching band at 1 570-1 640 cm⁻¹ instead of the normal conjugated ketones (1 650-1 720 cm⁻¹) may be due to reduction of the double bond character by resonance between two structures. Furthermore, shifting of the acetyl CO to 1 665 cm⁻¹ instead of 1 720 cm⁻¹ indicates the effect of conjugation of CO with a C=N double bond. The stretching bands at 1 690-1 500 cm⁻¹ probably result from the second conjugated CO involved in hydrogen bonding. In addition the large shift and broadening of the NH stretching band at 3 110-3 220 cm⁻¹ and the shift and reduction of the second CO stretching band can only result from a strong hydrogen bonding as shown in the above structures. The hydrazono structure to similar type of compounds has also been assigned by others^{2,3}.

1-Guanyl (2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-3-phenylamino-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles; To 2-arylhydrazono-1-

phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione (0.001 mol) dissolved in acetic acid (10-15 ml), was added to a solution of aminoguanidine nitrate/2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (10-15 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool overnight and the resulting crystals were recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 82° (Found: N, 29.16; C, 53.49. C₁₇H₁₅N₅O₅ calcd. for: N, 29.31; C, 52.40%); λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 244, 251 and 370 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 590 (-N=N), 1 620 (-C=N- or -C=C-), 3 120 and 750 cm⁻¹ (phenyl); δ (CDCl₃) 2.76 (3H, CH₃), 8.87 (H, NHC₆H₅), 11.37 (2H, NH₂) and 7.1-7.8 (10-ArH).

The physical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. P. Bhatnagar, Head, Department of Chemistry, Jiwaji University, for facilities.

References

- G. C. GERRITSEN and W. E. DALVI, *Diabetes*, 1965, **14**, 507; H. G. GARG and S. S. JOSHI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 946; H. G. GARG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 563; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 948; H. G. GARG and P. P. SINGH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 1104; R. B. PATHAK and S. C. BABEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1103; U. WRZEJONO, K. PIETKIRWEIZ and B. KRZYSZTOFIK, *Pharmazie*, 1978, **33**, 266; T. O. SHARMA, M. M. BOKADIA and N. J. PODDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 238.
- H. C. YAO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 2959.
- G. ALLEN and R. A. DEVEK, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1966, 161; D. O. NONABEL, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 1869; EN-CHULIN and M. R. VAN DERMARK, *J. Chem. Soc. Chem. Commun.*, 1982, 1178; P. COURTOT, R. PICHON and J. L. SAINT, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1976, 1176; J. E. McMURRY and M. SILVESTRI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, **40**, 1502; T. LOKHO and C. WONG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **39**, 3453.

[1,2,4]Triazino[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino-[5,6-c]cinnolin-9-one

H. K. GAKHAR*, (Ms.) RAMAN GUPTA

and

SHASHI BHUSHAN GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University,
Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 5 June 1989, accepted 21 November 1989

IN continuation of our work to synthesise heterocyclics by new routes, an attempt has been made to synthesise 10-methyl-11H,13H-[1,2,4]triazino[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-c]cinnolin-11-one (3a; R=R'=H) by refluxing equimolar quantities of 3-bromo-4-hydroxycinnoline (2) with 4-amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazine (1). But both the reactants were recovered in